

IMPROVEMENT OF THERMAL STORAGE SYSTEM IN RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS' RETROFIT

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In present paper the toolkit with holistic approach to energy retrofit of residential buildings is presented. This toolkit is under development within EU funded project HEART where step towards self-sufficient heating and cooling of building is made. The paper is focused on experimental investigation of sensible thermal storage improvement with phase change materials (PCMs) encapsulated in spherical modules.

HEART TOOLKIT

Retrofit of building sector represents a great challenge where majority of buildings retrofit are partially renovated by applying only one solution without consideration to the rest of the building system. That is why Holistic Energy & Architectural Retrofit Toolkit (HEART) was proposed. This toolkit is based on the synergistic interaction between technologies integrated in the system which are under development within HEART project.

In this project step towards self-sufficient heating and cooling of building is made with increase in on-site use of self-produced energy in PV from solar energy. Heat or cold is stored in thermal storage via DC heat pump that is connected to PV. This reduces daily mismatch between production from solar energy and thermal demand.

IMPROVED THERMAL STORAGE

Experimental investigation of sensible thermal storage improvement by implementing 30% of PCM was conducted. Measurements of three 100 L tanks connected in series with 576 PCM modules was performed and compared with thermal storage of water only – based on stored energy.

CONCLUSIONS

Latent thermal storage can store up to 68% more heat per same volume than sensible one. The biggest advantage of PCMs is in thermal storage in applications that needs narrow temperature range of storing energy (heat or cold).

KEYWORDS:

Retrofit, On-site RES utilization, Phase change materials (PCMs), Latent thermal storage